

The Modeling of a Mini-Grid with MicrogridsPy for rural electrification: Case of Kingwaya Village, D R Congo

- Edgard **BALENGWA ELENGI**, Minister of Water Resources and Electricity,
D R Congo
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Executive Summary:

This study investigates the optimal configuration of a renewable-based microgrid for Kingwaya, a remote village in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) that is not connected to the national grid. Using the MicrogridsPy modeling tool, several scenarios were evaluated to measure the technical and economic performance of different energy mixes, focusing on renewable energy integration and demand-side strategies.

The Base Case scenario, though affordable, depends heavily on diesel and achieves only 35.6% renewable penetration. Scenarios aiming for 60% and 80% renewable shares require significantly larger solar and battery systems, which increase both costs and energy curtailment. In contrast, the Daytime Load Management scenario presents the most cost-effective outcome, aligning energy use with solar availability, thus reducing storage needs while maintaining up to 76% renewable energy use.

The results underline the importance of load-shifting policies, such as time-of-use tariffs, and the promotion of clean cooking and efficient appliances. By combining both approaches, rural mini-grids can become more economically viable and technically balanced. This strategy directly supports DRC’s goal of reaching 60% electrification by 2030, offering a sustainable and replicable model for rural energy access.

By 2030, while ensuring that solutions remain sustainable, scalable, and adapted to rural realities.

1. Introduction

The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) has immense renewable energy potential, especially in hydropower (over 100,000 MW) and solar energy, thanks to high solar irradiation. Yet, less than 3% of this potential is currently exploited, and rural electrification remains below 3% (World Bank data, s.d.).

The village of Kingwaya, a remote off-grid community, illustrates these challenges. National electricity production (2,500–3,000 MW) is over 95% hydro-based, with nearly 60% used by the mining sector, while households receive only about 20% (Société Nationale d'Electricité SNEL, 2023). Rural populations' limited ability to pay for electricity discourages private investment, leaving most of the electrification responsibility to the State.

To address this, the government aims to reach a 62% electrification rate by 2030 through large hydro projects, hybrid solar systems, and mini-grid deployment in rural areas (MRHE, 2025).

Simulation tools like MicrogridsPy are key in shaping energy policy and supporting the design of technically and economically viable mini-grid systems adapted to local needs.

This study focuses on optimizing a microgrid for Kingwaya with high renewable energy integration. Three scenarios are tested using MicrogridsPy:

1. A baseline case;
2. Optimization with 60% and 80% renewable energy share;
3. Optimization with daytime load management.

Results will guide scalable solutions toward universal access.

Figure 1: Kingwaya village, Kivu province, DRCongo (ANSER, 2021)

2. Methodology:

2.1. Resources and demand assessment

Kingwaya village is located in an isolated area, far from the existing electrical grid. The nearest connection point is approximately 77 kilometers away. The village also benefits from strong solar potential.

Figure 2: Solar PV electricity production and monthly in-plane irradiation (Anon., s.d.)(Source: PVGIS Database)

A diesel generator will be installed as a backup energy source to handle peak demand, low solar radiation periods, or nighttime supply.

Demand assessment was carried out using a bottom-up approach through RAMP software, based primarily on usage behavior and appliance culture for each user group and subgroup. The process includes defining user categories, identifying appliances, characterizing users and their appliances, setting operating time windows, and applying load factors to generate a detailed minute-by-minute energy consumption profile.

Users' breakdown:

User type	User	Number	Proportion %
Dwellings	Low income	200	50%
	Medium income	100	30%
	High Income	35	20%
Commercials	Phone charging	15	40%
	Shop	18	50%
	Printing	6	5%
Community buildings	Mill	5	5%
	School	6	93%
	Hight School	2	5%
	Water system	1	1%
	Hospital	1	1%

The demand simulation was carried out over a 5-year period:

- The first year's load curve was modeled using RAMP, reflecting the current situation in the village. Second year was assumed first year applied growth rate of 2%.

- In the third year, we used RAMP to simulate the load curve, incorporating a 2% increase households and additional appliances such as irons, fans, TV, more lighting, etc. Fourth year replicated the third year's with 2% growth.
- The fifth-year load curve included another 2% growth and the addition of higher-energy appliances such as electric cooking, freezers, more lighting again, etc.

Load curve year 1

Load curve year 3

Load curve year 5

Year	Annual Energy Consumption (kWh)	Peak Power (kW)
Year 1	171,914.12	74.48
Year 2	257,953.44	129.80
Year 3	311,890.40	165.67

1.1. Scenarios

➤ Scenario 1: Base Case

Defined as the baseline scenario, done using MicrogridsPy software based on load data generated in RAMP, with cost optimization focused on minimizing Net Present Cost (NPC).

➤ Scenario 2: Optimization with Fixed Renewable Energy Rate

The base scenario is optimized with fixed renewable energy penetration rates of 60% and 80%, to assess the impact of increased renewable use on project cost and Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE).

➤ Scenario 3: Optimization with Daytime Load Management Policy

Analysis of demand curves shows that the consumption peak occurs at night, between 6 PM and 8 PM, requiring higher battery capacity or diesel usage, which increases project costs and LCOE. We propose

a policy encouraging daytime electricity use, by measures like higher tariff after 6 PM, to shift the demand peak to daytime hours, combine by the promotion of clean cooking alternatives.

Figure 3: Load curve demand daytime load management policy, year 1

Scenario Summary Table

Scenario	Load demand	Minimum Renewable energy used
Base Case	Baseline demand profile	No constraint
Fixed Renewable Penetration	Baseline demand profile	60% and 80%
Daytime Load Management Policy	Daytime consumption incentives	No constraint

3. Results:

The analysis clearly indicates that higher renewable penetration levels, such as 60% and 80% require substantial investments in both photovoltaic (PV) generation and battery storage. This is due to the need to ensure continuous energy availability, especially during nighttime or periods of low solar irradiation. As renewable shares increase, curtailment also rises, reflecting potential oversizing and underutilization during peak solar hours.

Conversely, the daytime load management policy scenario demonstrates that shifting consumption to daylight hours significantly reduces reliance on both battery storage and diesel backup systems. This approach leverages the natural solar generation curve, allowing for better alignment between supply and demand. As a result, overall system costs (NPC and LCOE) are reduced, and system efficiency improves without compromising renewable penetration levels.

These findings underscore the importance of demand-side strategies in complementing supply-side infrastructure, especially in off-grid, cost-sensitive environments.

Figure 4: Cost evolution

Figure 5: Microgrid installed capacity

Scenario Comparison

Table 1 : Scenario result summary

Scenario	Solar PV (kW)	Diesel Generator (kW)	Battery (kWh)	NPC (kUSD)	LCOE (USD/kWh)	Curtailement (%)	Renewable penetration (%)
Base case	65	138	47	436,56	0,443	13,46	35,64
Minimum renewable 60%	135	78	377	454,97	0,4616	19,23	74
Minimum renewable 80%	199	33	630	504,03	0,5114	40,05	91
Daytime Policy	71	72	65	279.27	0,3915	23,41	54,65

➤ Base Case

This reference scenario is heavily reliant on diesel generation (138 kW), supported by a modest solar PV capacity (65 kW) and minimal battery storage (47 kWh). It delivers a low renewable energy share (35.64%), with the advantage of a simpler and less capital-intensive system. However, it entails a high dependency on fuel supply and results in higher greenhouse gas emissions.

➤ 60% and 80% minimum Renewable Penetration

To achieve higher renewable integration (up to 91%), these scenarios require larger PV installations (135–199 kW) and significant battery storage (377–630 kWh). Diesel capacity is reduced (78 to 33 kW), indicating a move toward decarbonization. However, curtailment rates rise sharply (up to 40%), reflecting inefficiencies from oversizing. These systems are technically cleaner but demand substantial investments and precise planning to avoid underutilization.

➤ Daytime load demand Management policy

This scenario demonstrates the benefits of **shifting demand to daylight hours**, leveraging solar availability to balance generation and consumption. It requires **moderate PV capacity (71–101 kW)**, **lower diesel use (72–47 kW)**, and **smaller battery banks (65–201 kWh)**. With a **renewable share of 54–76%**, this configuration significantly reduces system costs (NPC, LCOE) and complexity, while maintaining technical reliability.

Figure 6: Energy Balance - Base case

Figure 7: Energy Balance - 60% minimum Renewable energy

Figure 8: Energy Balance - 80% minimum Renewable energy

Figure 9: Energy Balance - Daytime management policy

Key Technical Insights

- **System sizing** is directly influenced by the load curve: night peaks require more battery storage, while daytime demand aligns naturally with PV output.
- **Curtailment increases** with high PV capacity when consumption is not adjusted, emphasizing the role of demand-side flexibility.
- **Battery optimization** is essential for balancing reliability and cost, especially in rural settings where oversizing may not be sustainable.
- **Load management unlocks performance:** The Daytime Policy scenario shows that smart consumption patterns can enable high renewable use at lower cost.

In summary, **technical performance improves with higher renewable use**, but without load management, systems may become oversized and economically inefficient. The **daytime policy scenario offers the most balanced solution**, technically and economically, making it the most suitable for rural electrification efforts like that in Kingwaya.

Figure 10: Average Energy Usage by Technology

5. Discussion:

The results of this study offer several key insights into the optimal design and deployment of microgrids for rural electrification in the Democratic Republic of Congo. Firstly, the scenario incorporating daytime load management emerges as the most cost-effective, with the lowest Net Present Cost (NPC) and Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE). By encouraging energy consumption during daylight hours, this approach takes advantage of solar generation when it is most abundant, thereby reducing the reliance on battery storage and diesel generators.

In contrast, scenarios targeting high renewable energy penetration rates (60% and 80%) demonstrate clear environmental benefits but come at a higher economic cost. These scenarios require larger PV and battery capacities and result in increased energy curtailment, highlighting a trade-off between sustainability and financial viability.

Moreover, the analysis confirms that hybrid microgrids—combining solar, diesel, and battery systems—represent a technically viable and scalable solution for electrifying off-grid communities such as Kingwaya. The study also underlines the importance of demand-side policies, including time-of-use pricing or clean cooking programs, which can shift energy usage to more favorable times and reduce overall system costs.

Finally, the use of simulation tools like MicrogridsPy proves essential in supporting evidence-based policy and investment planning, allowing stakeholders to explore various configurations and outcomes before implementation.

Based on the study findings, the following policy actions are recommended:

- Encourage daytime electricity consumption to align demand with solar availability, thereby minimizing battery and diesel usage and reducing overall system costs.
- Promote clean cooking and efficient appliances, particularly for domestic and productive use. Lowering nighttime electricity demand helps reduce required system size and limits cost increases related to PV and storage capacity.

By combining both measures, it is possible to develop more efficient and affordable mini-grid systems, ensuring broader access to sustainable electricity in rural areas.

For future research directions:

- Analyze the effects of different load growth patterns on system design and cost.
- Evaluate the integration potential of complementary renewable sources such as small-scale hydro.
- Perform sensitivity analyses on fuel prices and technology cost fluctuations to improve investment planning.

7. Conclusion:

This study demonstrated the value of using microgrid modeling tools, such as MicrogridsPy, to design optimized electrification solutions for rural, off-grid communities like Kingwaya village in the Democratic Republic of Congo.

Five different scenarios were analyzed, with varying renewable energy shares and demand management strategies.

Key lessons learned include:

- Higher renewable penetration (60%–80%) leads to increased PV and battery sizing, but also higher curtailment and system costs.
- The base case is low-cost but environmentally unsustainable due to high diesel reliance.
- The daytime load management policy offers the best balance between cost, technical performance, and renewable share, by aligning energy use with solar availability.

Recommendations:

- Adopt demand-side management policies, such as time-of-use tariffs, to shift consumption to daytime and reduce dependence on storage and diesel generation.
- Promote clean cooking and energy-efficient appliances to reduce peak evening loads and overall demand, contributing to system downsizing and cost reduction.
- Combine both strategies to achieve affordable, efficient, and low-emission microgrids tailored to rural realities.

- Use simulation tools like MicrogridsPy to support decision-making, plan energy infrastructure, and evaluate policy impacts before implementation.

These actions will help scale up rural electrification efforts across the DRC, ensuring greater energy access while promoting sustainability and affordability.

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